

Impact of Injuries on Lower Extremity and Fitness Parameter of Baseball Players

Dr. Kalane Ravindra Ajinath

Head & Director of Physical Education and Sports), HSBPVT'S GOI Faculty of Engineering, Kasthi, Tal-Shrigonda Dist- Ahilyanagar

Corresponding Author – Dr. Kalane Ravindra Ajinath

DOI - 10.5281/zenodo.19510618

Abstract:

The aim of this study was to determine the relation of injuries on lower extremity and fitness parameter of Baseball players. Thirty samples age between 17–25-year as inter collegiate Baseball players participated in inter collegiate tournaments season of 2025-2026 participated in the organized inter collegiate competition held under the Savitribai Phule Pune University, Pune from the HSBPVT'S GOI Faculty of Engineering, Kasthi, Tal- Shrigonda Dist- Ahilyanagar, they were selected as sample through the purposively sampling technique. In this study fitness tests were used to measure the subjects' fitness. A questionnaire was used for the collection of sport injuries. Correlation coefficient was used to examine the relationship between variables.

Keywords: Sport Injuries, Fitness, Lower Extremity and Baseball Players

Introduction:

Today the majority of players have achieved to correct understanding of sport and physical activity in terms of fitness & prevention of injuries, but the lack of fitness and physical injuries awareness in those one who participated in favorite sport field may cause to unexpected physical losses; this may also label a negative mark in the field of sport; not only the lack of information in terms of sport makes athletes expose to any injuries but also their psychological conditions get into risky setting so that any physical activities disappear from athletes sport life. Fitness factors and sport injuries are dependent completely together influencing each other at the same time; therefore, any struggle through athletes' physical abilities cause to prevention of an injury is crucial step to reach physical training worthwhile goals.

Material and Method:

The present study was descriptive survey research method. Thirty samples age between 17–25-year as inter collegiate Baseball players participated in inter collegiate tournaments season of 2025-2026 participated in the organized inter collegiate competition held under the Savitribai Phule Pune University, Pune from the HSBPVT'S GOI Faculty of Engineering, Kasthi, Tal-Shrigonda Dist- Ahilyanagar, they were selected as sample through the purposively sampling technique. Researcher administered questionnaire was used to obtain information of injury. In this study the stopwatch was used to measure time of the tests. The box of measuring flexibility of lower limbs used for gathering sport injuries that each Baseball players marks faced injuries. Correlation coefficient method was used to examine relationship between the variables.

Analysis of the Result:

Table No. 1: Descriptive Statistics

Variable	Mean	SD	Min	Max
Flexibility	31	6.7	12	45
Agility	18.3	1.09	21.5	21.5

Table No. 2: Distribution of Sport Injuries in Lower Extremity

Limb	No of Injuries	
Leg	Distribution	13
	Percentage	19.1
Knee	Distribution	22
	Percentage	32.4
Ankle	Distribution	6
	Percentage	8.8

Table No. 3: Distribution and Percentage of Injuries in Lower Extremity

Type of Injury	Stretches & Wounds	Contusion	Strain	Bruises	Muscular Stretches
Distribution	14	2	3	24	15
Percentage	24.6	2.14	5.1	42.1	26.3

Table No. 4.: Description of fitness records of subjects

Variable		Good	Moderate	Weak
Flexibility	Distribution	41	---	---
	Percentage	100	---	---
Agility	Distribution	9	32	---
	Percentage	22	78	---

Table No. 5: Coefficient of K-Square to find relation between fitness and sport injuries

Variable	K-Square	Sig.
Flexibility	-0.026	0.751
Agility	0.72	0.396

In the table no. 5 mentioned there are no any significant differences between flexibility, agility and the lower extremity of injuries ($p > 0.05$).

Discussion:

The results of the study showed that the most injuries among baseball players relate to contusion, strain and stretch. The results of the study Hoy and et al (1992) consider contusion and stretch as the usual injuries in sport players; Thomas and David (1998) reported contusion and stretch as common injuries Gall et al (2008); besides all these researchers consider the lack of fitness as the most vital factor for any sport injury. The present athletes of the study were in good level of flexibility whereas other factors were in moderate level.

Conclusion:

On the basis of result obtained in study the researcher made the conclusion that show the there were no any significant differences between flexibility and agility of lower extremity ($p > 0.05$).

References:

1. Grote K, Lincoln TL, Gamble JG. Hip adductor injury in competitive swimmers. Am J Sports Med. 2004; 32(1):104–108.
2. Kennedy JC, Hawkins R, Krissoff WB. Orthopedic manifestations of swimming. Am J Sports Med. 1978; 6(6):309–322.

3. Keskinen K, Eriksson E, Komi P. Breaststroke swimmer's knee: a biomechanical and arthroscopic study. *Am J Sports Med.* 1980; 8(4):228–231.
4. McFarland EG, Wasik M. Injuries in female collegiate swimmers due to swimming and cross training. *Clin J Sport Med.* 1996; 6(3):178–182.
5. McMaster WC, Troup J. A survey of interfering shoulders pain in United States competitive swimmers. *Am J Sports Med.* 1993; 21(1):67–70.